

LEVERAGING DIGITAL HEALTH PLATFORMS TO EXPAND ACCESS TO SEXUAL AND REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH SERVICES ACCESS AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the effectiveness of digital health platforms in expanding undergraduate access to sexual and reproductive health services and information. Data were collected from 349 undergraduates' students at the university of Calabar through a self-administered online and paper based survey, utilizing the students' WhatsApp platform and a convenience sampling technique. The technology acceptance model was employed in the study. Findings revealed that less than half (42.1%) of the respondents were aware of digital health platforms for accessing sexual and reproductive health services and information. The data revealed a statistically significant association between place of residence and digital health platforms utilization. Although the majority of participants (n=202, 57.9%) were not aware of digital platforms, most (n=234, 67.1%) were willing to recommend digital health platforms for sexual and reproductive health information to their peers. Digital health platforms can be leveraged to improve access as digital technology has become a critical part of the youths' lives, by expanding digital health literacy and fostering inclusive, culturally sensitive platforms.

Keywords: Digital health platforms, Reproductive health services, Sexual, Undergraduates

INTRODUCTION

Access to sexual and reproductive health (SRH) services is a major global health issue, particularly for adolescents and young adults. Millions of young people around the world still face obstacles to receiving accurate SRH information and services. This circumstance contributes to high rates of unintended pregnancies, unsafe abortions, and sexually transmitted infections (STIs) (WHO, 2023). Each year, approximately 16 million girls aged 15 to 19 give birth globally, and complications related to pregnancy and childbirth are the leading causes of death for adolescent girls in low and middle-income countries (UNFPA, 2022). In sub-Saharan Africa, where nearly 60% of the population is under 25, young people often do not have access to complete sexuality education, private SRH services, or the supportive settings necessary for informed decision-making (Chandra-Mouli et al., 2019). These challenges highlights the urgent need to find new ways to improve SRH service delivery for this group.

Nigeria, with its large youth population, faces similar issues. Young people, especially undergraduates, are particularly susceptible due to their stage of development, peer influences, and transition to independence. The consequences are clear: there are high rates of unintended pregnancies, unsafe abortions, HIV, and other STIs. Cultural taboos, stigma, and lack of

information are major barriers that prevent students from accessing accurate and private SRH services (Odi et al., 2020). Additionally, SRH services in many universities lack adequate resources and are often not tailored to young adults' needs.

Access to SRH services among students is influenced by various related factors. These factors include the availability of youth-friendly services, societal attitudes, levels of SRH knowledge, gender issues, affordability, and how well health facilities can provide private care (Ninsiima et al., 2021). Importantly, social stigma and the fear of being judged by health providers keep many students from seeking contraceptives or HIV testing. The lack of privacy when accessing services also leads to unmet SRH needs. Therefore, tackling these barriers requires new strategies that are private, focused on youth, and address the digital realities of young people.

In recent years, digital health platforms (DHPs) have emerged as a game-changer in healthcare delivery globally. These platforms include mobile health apps, telemedicine services, online counseling, chatbots, and social media interventions (Ahmed et al., 2025). They offer unique chances to share SRH information, provide remote consultations, and connect users with services while ensuring confidentiality and privacy. For digital natives like college students, these platforms provide anonymity, convenience, and engaging interactions, which can encourage more people to seek SRH information and services. For instance, mobile apps and online communities have been shown to boost contraceptive awareness, expand access to emergency contraception, and support real-time counseling (Ippoliti & L'Engle, 2017). Evidence from some low and middle-income countries suggests that integrating digital platforms into SRH programs can significantly increase contraceptive use, enhance awareness of HIV, and reduce risky sexual behaviors (Chib et al., 2015).

While there is growing evidence about how well digital health innovations work in increasing access to SRH, few studies have focused specifically on undergraduate students in Nigeria. Most existing research looks at general adolescent populations or youth in urban areas, without considering the unique situation of university students (Akinsoji et al., 2015). Yet, undergraduate students are critical: they are tech-savvy, highly connected to digital platforms, and often in a stage of life marked by sexual experimentation and exposure to SRH risks. At the same time, they face barriers to traditional SRH services due to stigma, cultural norms, and infrastructure issues. Several studies (Adegbilero-Iwari, 2021; Anyaoku et al., 2015; Obasola, et al., 2016; Onwe & Okocha, 2019) have been carried out on the online health information seeking among undergraduates in Nigeria, however, limited studies have focused specifically on the utilization of DHPs for SRH. This gap highlights the need to explore how digital health platforms can help reduce inequalities in SRH service access for Nigerian undergraduates.

The aim of this study is to examine how digital health platforms can be used to expand SRH services among undergraduate students. Specifically, the study seeks to (1) assess the level of awareness and familiarity with digital health platforms providing sexual and reproductive health services, (2) examine the patterns of utilization and perceived helpfulness of digital health platforms for accessing sexual and reproductive health services among undergraduate students, (3) identify the reasons for preferring digital sexual and reproductive health platforms, and (4) identify the challenges faced by undergraduate students in accessing sexual and reproductive services through digital health platforms. We hypothesize that utilization of digital health platforms positively correlates with perceptions of helpfulness in addressing sexual and

reproductive needs of undergraduate students and undergraduate students who find digital health platforms helpful are more likely to recommend these platforms to their peers.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

This study is guided by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by Davis (1989) is rooted in the Theory of reasoned actions (Fishbein) and Theory of planned behaviour(Ajzen). The TAM explains what influences people's intentions and use of technology. The model posits that two primary factors which are Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) influences an individual's Behavioural Intention (BI) to use technology, which in turn determines the actual usage.

Applied to this study, Technology Acceptance Model provides a lens for understanding undergraduate students' adoption of Digital Health Platforms (DHPs) for sexual and Reproductive Health (SRH) services:

Perceived Usefulness (PU): Students who feel that digital health platforms increase access to timely, accurate, and private sexual and reproductive health information and services, like HIV testing or contraceptive counselling, are more likely to use them.

Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU): Students are more likely to embrace and continue using digital health platforms if they believe they are easy to use and convenient, particularly when accessed through well-known channels like WhatsApp.

Behavioural Intention (BI): Students are more likely to suggest digital health platforms to their peers when they perceive them as practical and user-friendly, which encourages adoption.

External Variables: Students' perceptions of usefulness and ease of use may be shaped by sociodemographic factors (e.g., age, gender, year of study, and place of residence), which in turn may influence behavioural intention and actual usage.

Utilizing the TAM which explains how perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness influence students' intentions and actual behaviours in adopting digital health technologies for SRH needs. Students are likely to utilize digital health platforms when they believe these platforms will enhance their access to confidential and accurate information. Where the platforms are easy to utilize and navigate without barriers, their use will be enhanced. Similarly external influence through peer recommendations also affects acceptance and utilization. Factors such as digital literacy, privacy concerns, social context, and user motivation play critical roles in adoption and sustained engagement with digital health interventions This framework provides a structured basis for examining the awareness, utilization, and willingness to recommend digital health platforms among undergraduates, while also highlighting how socio-demographic factors interact with the adoption of digital health.

METHODS

A cross-sectional survey was conducted between July and August, 2025 among undergraduate students of University of Calabar, South-south Nigeria. All undergraduate students at University of Calabar who were willing to respond to the questionnaire were eligible to participate while postgraduate students were excluded.

The study used a self-administered on-line survey using the mobile app Kobo Toolbox to recruit participants for the study via convenience sampling technique using the student online

WhatsApp groups. Due to the slow response rate, the study used a self-administered paper-based questionnaire to collect the remaining data which was then uploaded into the Kobo Toolbox through the convenience sampling technique with the help of five research assistants. Similar procedure was adopted by Ogundipe et al. (2025). The questionnaire contained 18 items related to demographic variables, awareness and utilization of digital health platforms for sexual and reproductive health services. The dependent variables were utilization of DHP for SRH services and willingness to recommend DHP. The independent variables were helpfulness of DHP and socio-demographic characteristics such as age, sex, year of study, and place of residence.

The Leslie Kish formula (1965) was used to estimate the sample size, employing a standard normal deviate of 1.96 corresponding to a 95% confidence level. A prevalence of utilizing online resources for sexual health of 59.9% among undergraduate students in Nigeria by Adegbilero et al. (2021), and a desired precision level of 5% were applied. A minimum sample size of 369 was calculated.

All administered questionnaires were checked for completeness. The questionnaires were filled out appropriately by 349 respondents and these were used for data analysis. Respondents' demographic characteristics measured as categorical variables were analyzed using frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test of independence was performed to ascertain the association between the variables of interest with a p-value of <0.05 . All analysis were conducted using Stata version 18.

Ethical consideration

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the University of Calabar Research Ethical Review Board, Directorate of Research and Development, University of Calabar (UC/DR&D/RERB/56).

Results

The study included 349 respondents, of whom 53.6 % were males and 83.1% were below 25 years, old with about 64.5% in their fourth year of study. A large majority of the participants (82.0%) resided off campus (Table 1).

Undergraduate students' awareness of DHPs for accessing SRH services is summarize in Table 2. Of the 147 respondents (42.1%) who were aware of digital health platforms, 86 (58.5%) were familiar most with WhatsApp/telegram, and for 93 (63.3%), social media was the first source of knowledge about digital platforms. Data also revealed that contraceptive counseling and STI/HIV information were the services most accessed by respondents using digital health platforms (n=46, 45.1%).

Table 3 shows that 69.4% of all the students who were aware of DHPs for SRH had used such platforms to access SRH information and services. Regarding frequency of use, 67 (65.7%) participants used digital health platforms occasionally, while 58 (56.9%) found them very helpful. Slightly more than half of the respondents (=179, 51.3%) showed no preference between seeking sexual and reproductive health information online or in persons. Concerning reasons for using digital health platforms, 66 (64.7%) indicated accessibility and convenience as motivating factors, while limited trust in online sources was reported as a challenge by 35 (34.3%) respondents. WhatsApp was reported as the most preferred platforms for receiving

sexual and reproductive health information by 43 (42.2%) participants. Although the majority of the participants (n=202, 57.9%) were not aware of digital platforms, most (n=234, 67.1%) were willing to recommend digital health platforms for sexual and reproductive health information to their peers.

Table 4 displays the association between perceived helpfulness of digital health platforms and both utilization and willingness to recommend the platforms to peers. No statistically significant association was found between these variables. Data reveals a statistically significant association between place of residence and digital health platforms utilization (Table 5).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of respondents

Characteristics	N = 349 (%)
Age in years, mean \pm SD	22.86 \pm 3.8
Age group	
<25	290 (83.1)
>25	59 (16.9)
Sex	
Male	187 (53.6)
Female	162 (44.4)
Year of study	
Year 1	22 (6.3)
Year 2	34 (9.7)
Year 3	42 (12.0)
Year 4	225 (64.5)
Year 5	20 (5.7)
Year 6	6 (1.7)
Place of residence	
On campus	63 (18.0)
Off campus	286 (82.0)
Faculty	
Agriculture	2 (0.6)
Allied Medical Sciences	27 (7.7)
Arts and Humanities	5 (1.4)
Basic Medical Sciences	20 (5.7)
Biological Sciences	12 (3.4)
Clinical Sciences	102 (29.2)
Computing	4 (1.2)
Dentistry	12 (3.4)
Educational Foundation	3 (0.9)
Engineering	7 (2.0)
Environmental Sciences	3 (0.9)
Law	4 (1.2)
Management Sciences	12 (3.4)
Medical Laboratory Sciences	33 (9.5)

Pharmacy	25 (7.2)
Physical Sciences	1 (0.3)
Science Education	3 (0.9)
Social Sciences	74 (21.2)

Table 2: Awareness of digital health platforms

Variables	Number (349), n (%)
Aware of digital health platforms	
No	202 (57.9)
Yes	147 (42.1)
Respondents aware of digital health platforms (n=147)	
Digital platforms familiar with	86 (58.5)
WhatsApp/telegram based health support group	55 (37.4)
Health mobile apps	42 (28.6)
Sexual and reproductive health websites	21 (14.3)
SMS based information services	6 (4.1)
Others	
Respondents aware of digital health platforms (n=147)	
First source of digital platforms	
Friends	35 (23.8)
Social media	93 (63.3)
School health services	9 (6.1)
NGO outreach	10 (6.8)

Table 3: Utilization of Digital health platforms

Variables	Number (427), n (%)
Respondents aware of digital health platforms (n=147)	
Ever use DHPs for SRH services and information	
Yes	102 (69.4)
NO	45 (30.6)
SRH Services accessed	
Contraceptive counseling	46 (45.1)
STI /HIV information	46 (45.1)
Sexual violence and coercion	26 (25.5)
Pregnancy option counseling	27 (26.5)
Others	8 (7.8)
Respondents who have utilized a digital health platform (n=102)	
Frequency of use of digital health platforms for SRH	
Daily	13 (12.8)
Weekly	14 (13.7)
Monthly	8 (7.8)
Occasionally	67 (65.7)

Respondents who have utilized a digital health platform (n=102)	
Helpfulness of digital health platforms in addressing SRH needs	
Very helpful	58 (56.9)
Somewhat helpful	24 (23.5)
Neutral	19 (18.6)
Not sure	1 (1.0)
Preference to seek SRH information or services online rather than in person	
Strongly prefer online	64 (18.3)
Somewhat prefer online	45 (12.9)
No preference	179 (51.3)
Somewhat prefer in person	31 (8.9)
Strongly prefer in person	30 (8.6)
Respondents who have utilized a digital health platform (n=102)	
Reasons for using digital SRH platforms	
Accessibility/convenience	66 (64.7)
Confidentiality	44 (43.1)
Reduced stigma	25 (24.5)
Cost effectiveness	20 (19.6)
Others	5 (4.9)
Challenges faced accessing SRH services through digital platforms	
Lack of awareness	25 (24.5)
Limited trust in online sources	35 (34.3)
Concerns about data privacy	28 (27.5)
Poor internet connectivity	23 (22.6)
Difficulty navigating platforms	16 (15.7)
Cost of data/subscription	22 (21.6)
Others	2 (2.0)
Respondents who have utilized a digital health platform (n=102)	
Digital platforms preferred for receiving SRH information	
Mobile Apps	37 (36.3)
WhatsApp	43 (42.2)
Instagram	15 (14.7)
YouTube	23 (22.6)
Others	8 (7.8)
Willingness to recommend digital SRH platforms to peers	
Yes	234 (67.1)
No	20 (5.7)
Not sure	95 (27.2)

Table 5: Association between perceived helpfulness and digital health platforms use and willingness to recommend to peers

Variables	Total	Use of digital platforms		X ²	P-value	Willing to recommend platforms to peers			X ²	P-value
		No	Yes			No	Not sure	Yes		
Perceived helpfulness										
Helpful	82	2 (2.4)	80 (97.6)			2(2.4)	9 (11.0)	71 (86.6)		
Not sure	20	2 (10.0)	18 (90.0)	2.4396	0.118	1 (5.0)	2 (10.0)	17 (85.0)	0.3774	0.828

*significant @ p<0.05 level, δLikelihood ratio chi-square

Table 4: Association between socio-demographic variables and digital health platforms use and willingness to recommend to peers

Total	Use of digital bplatforms		X ²	P-value	Willing to recommend platforms to peers			X ²	P-value	
	No	Yes			No	Not sure	Yes			
187	132 (70.6)	55 (29.4)	0.0067	0.935	12 (6.4)	50 (26.7)	125 (66.8)	0.3682	0.832	
162	115 (71.0)	47 (29.0)			8 (4.9)	45 (27.8)	109 (67.3)			
290	203 (70.0)	87 (30.0)	0.4964	0.481	16 (5.5)	78 (26.9)	196 (67.6)	0.2764	0.871	
59	44 (74.6)	15 (25.4)			4 (6.8)	17 (28.8)	38 (64.1)			
98	73 (74.5)	25 (25.1)	0.9097	0.340	4 (4.1)	30 (30.6)	170 (67.7)	1.2841	0.526	
251	174 (69.3)	77 (30.7)			16 (6.4)	65 (25.9)	191 (68.3)			
286	212 (74.1)	74 (25.9)	8.6074	0.003*	16 (5.6)	79 (27.6)	166 (66.8)	43	0.1619	0.922
63	35 (55.6)	28 (44.4)			4 (6.4)	16 (25.4)	43 (68.3)			

*significant @ p<0.05 level, δLikelihood ratio chi-square

Discussion

This study provided insights into how digital health platforms (DHPs) can be leveraged to expand sexual and reproductive health (SRH) services among undergraduate students. It examined the relationship between perceived helpfulness, socio-demographic variables, utilization, and willingness to recommend these platforms. The chi-square test showed no

significant association for most variables examined. However, a significant relationship was found between place of residence and use of DHPs.

A strength of this study is the inclusion of students from several faculties. The results revealed low awareness of DHPs for SRH services and information, with only four out of ten respondents aware of these platforms. A similar study in Nigeria by Ogundipe et al (2025) among students in South-west Nigeria reported low awareness (16.8%) of digital mental health platforms despite high ownership of digital devices. Similarly, Ibegbulam (2018), found that a significant obstacle to accessing information is the lack of knowledge about quality websites. A study by Ikpi et al., (2024) had shown that physicians extensively use social media to convey health-related information to the public. Given the respondents' low awareness, they might be missing out on reliable information. Onyechi (2023) found that young people consider social media as unreliable; limited trust in online sources was also reported by three in ten of the students in our study. This lack of trust may explain their low enthusiasm for discovering DHPs available for accessing SRH information and services. Obasola and Agunbiade (2016) reported that only 15% of students sought sexual and reproductive health information online. Discussing and accessing SRH information is often perceived as taboo among youth, with such behaviour labeled promiscuous, which may contribute to low awareness of DHPs for SRH information.

Among those aware of DHP for SRH, nearly seven out of ten respondents have used a DHP to access SRH services and information. This finding aligns with the high utilization rate of 84.8% reported by Ogundipe et al. (2025) among undergraduate students using DHPs for mental health services. This high utilization in our study may be attributed to the over representation of clinical students (29.2%), who may be more aware of DHPs for health care services and information. This is consistent with findings by Chereka et al, (2025), who reported that a significant proportion (81.3%) of undergraduate health sciences students in Ethiopia had good awareness and 56.5% used the internet for health information. Onyechi (2023) also found that the participants actively search social media for health-related information. Onyechi (2023) also found that participants actively search social media for health-related information, particularly about mental, preventive, and lifestyle health. These findings suggest that awareness positively influences utilization.

Contrary to some previous studies (Anyanwu, 2024; Alhaji et al., 2025) no significant association was found between socio-demographic variables such as age, sex and year of study and use of DHPs or likelihood of recommending them. Place of residence was the only demographic variable showing significant relationship. This contrast with Alhassan et al. (2019), who found that male and younger adults were more likely than females to use mobile phones for STI education and prevention. Similar to our findings regarding year of study, Montagni et al. (2018) did not find any association between year of study and digital health use among students at the University of Bordeaux, France. Our results also revealed that students in year 4 – 6 were slightly more likely to use DHPs. This aligns with Chereka et al. (2025), who found that health science students in their third year and above were 2.33 times more likely than those in second year and below to use the internet for health information. The majority, six in ten respondents use DHP to utilize SRH occasionally. This contrast with Ibegbulam et al. (2018), who found that the vast majority (45%) search for information about reproductive health online each month, also 24% use the internet weekly and 6% daily. More importantly, 67.1%

of our study participants were willing to recommend DHPs for SRH to their peers despite low awareness.

One limitation of the study is that it was conducted at the University of Calabar, and findings may not be generalized to all students in Nigeria.

Conclusion and recommendations

The study highlights the potential of digital health platforms to enhance access to SRH services and information among undergraduate students. In spite of low awareness, a majority of those aware actively use them. Also, most students showed willingness to recommend them to their peers. SRH is an essential aspect of achieving the sustainable development goal 3 of ensuring healthy lives and promoting wellbeing of all at all ages. Digital health platforms can be leveraged as digital technology has become a critical part of the lives of the youths by expanding digital health literacy and fostering inclusive, culturally sensitive platforms. Factual and reliable information through the school health unit can be made accessible to students WhatsApp group as it was reported to be their preferred means of accessing SRH.

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